

Tool 1

Baseline Data of Antenatal Mother

Instruction: Kindly go through the items given below and provide the appropriate answer by filling in the space or putting a tick (√) mark.

1. Code:
2. Age:_____ (in years)
3. Education:_____
4. Occupation:_____
5. Monthly family income._____ (in Rs)
6. Type of family:
 - Joint
 - Nuclear
7. Religion:
 - Hindu
 - Muslim
 - Christian
 - Any other Specify:_____
8. Source of information on newborn care (Multiple options can be selected) TV
 - Radio
 - Internet
 - Health care worker
 - Mass education
 - Any other specify: _____
9. Last menstrual period:
10. Period of gestation: _____
11. Are you confident in providing newborn care?
 - a) Yes
 - b) No
12. Are you prepared to provide newborn care?
 - a) Yes
 - b) No

Tool 2: Structured knowledge questionnaire on newborn care

Instruction: Kindly go through the items given below and circle the alphabet of the appropriate answer.

A. Thermoregulation

1. What is Thermoregulation?
 - A. It is a process of maintenance of normal body temperature in newborn
 - B. It is a process of preventing Heat loss in newborns.
 - C. It is a process of preventing high body temperature in newborns.
 - D. It is a process of preventing low body temperature in newborns.

2. What is the normal body temperature in newborn(in Celsius)?
 - A. 36.5 - 37.5
 - B. 37.6 - 38.5
 - C. 38.6 -39.5
 - D. 39.6- 40.5

3. In which season may newborns have low body temperature?
 - A. Rainy
 - B. Summer
 - C. Winter
 - D. All seasons

4. Which among the following is **NOT** a cause of low body temperature in a newborn?
 - A. Baby's Body organ are not developed
 - B. Due to vigorous movement of baby
 - C. Hereditary
 - D. The thermoregulation centre is not developed

5. A newborn loses heat by the conversion of water present on the body surface into vapour. Which type of heat loss is this?
 - A. Conduction
 - B. Convection
 - C. Evaporation
 - D. Radiation

6. Which among the following statements is **TRUE** related to body temperature in newborns?
 - A. Environmental condition does not affect the baby's body temperature.
 - B. Heat loss in newborns can be prevented by skin-to-skin contact of mother and newborn.
 - C. Heat loss is the same in adults and newborns.
 - D. There is no life-threatening complication

7. Which among the following signs indicates low body temperature in a newborn?
 - A. bluish extremities
 - B. Convulsion
 - C. Jaundice
 - D. Sweating

8. Mrs. X wants to maintain the warmth of her baby. Which among the following mentioned measures is best suited to achieve this?
- A. Keep the baby under sunlight
 - B. Placing a blanket under the newborn.
 - C. Use of a cradle
 - D. Use of double-layered cloth to wrap

B. Breastfeeding

9. All of the following are the benefits of breastfeeding to the newborn,
EXCEPT:
- A. Boost immunity
 - B. Low risk of allergy
 - C. Low risk of indigestion
 - D. Treats anomalies
10. Which among the following is a benefit of breastfeeding to the mother?
- A. Increases weight
 - B. Low risk of cancer
 - C. Reduces hair falls
 - D. Reduces infections
11. When should breastfeeding be initiated (in hours) after the delivery?
- A. $\frac{1}{2}$
 - B. 1
 - C. 2
 - D. 3
12. How often should a baby be breastfed?
- A. Every $\frac{1}{2}$ an hour
 - B. Every hourly
 - C. On demand
 - D. Once every 3 hours
13. How long (in min) breastfeeding should be given during each feed?
- A. 5- 10
 - B. 15- 20
 - C. 25- 30
 - D. 35- 40
14. How many months of exclusive breastfeeding should be given to the newborn?
- A. 2
 - B. 4
 - C. 6
 - D. 8

15. Which of the following is the proper holding of the breast during feeding a newborn?

- A. C hold (thumb at the upper part of the breast and all 4 fingers in the lower part of the breast)
- B. V hold(use the index at the upper part of the breast and 3rd finger to grasp the lower part of the breast)
- C. E hold (use index at upper part of breast, 3rd and 4th fingers to grasp in lower part of breast)
- D. Any hold is suitable.

16. Which among the following positions should the mother use during feeding the newborn?

- A. Lying
- B. Sit straight
- C. Slightly bent forward
- D. Any position

17. Identify the proper latch

- A. The newborn's mouth is wide open, the chin touches the breast, the chest touches the chest of the mother
- B. Most of the areola inside the newborn's mouth, the chin touches the breast, the chest touches the chest of the mother
- C. Newborn sucks nipple, baby lies on lap, chest won't touch mother's chest.
- D. Newborn's mouth wide open, baby lies on the lap, chest won't touch mother's chest.

18. Identify the proper technique to be used by the mother to hold the newborn while breastfeeding.

- A. Sit straight, use a pillow under the baby, rest the baby's head on the mother's elbow joint, and rest the baby's body on the mother's forearm
- B. Slightly bend forward, baby lies on lap, support with non-dominant hand
- C. Keep pillow behind mother's back, baby lies on lap, support with non-dominant hand.
- D. Turn to the right lying position, rest the baby's head on the mother's upper arm, and rest the baby's body on the bed.

19. Identify the proper burping position.

- A. Baby over the shoulder
- B. Baby sitting position over your Lap
- C. Baby lying prone over your lap
- D. All of the above

20. Which among the following statements is **TRUE** about breastfeeding?

- A. Breastfeeding on lying position is safe for the newborn
- B. Breastfeeding spoils the physical structure of the mother.
- C. Breastmilk contains the necessary nutrients required for the newborn.
- D. One side breast should be fed in a day.

21. Which among the following is the immediate complication to the mother due to improper breastfeeding technique?

- A. Cracked nipple
- B. Decreased milk secretion
- C. Inversion of the nipple
- D. Skin infection

22. Which among the following is a complication of improper breastfeeding technique in a newborn?

- A. Aspiration
- B. Fever
- C. Infections
- D. Rashes

23. Mrs. M complains about less milk secretion. What measures can help Mrs. M to enhance milk secretion?

- A. Breast sucking by newborn 2 hourly
- B. Eat more rice items
- C. Exercise for 10 minutes
- D. Walk for 10 minutes

C. Personal hygiene

24. What is the purpose of diaper care?

- A. To maintain hygiene
- B. To promote growth
- C. To enhance relaxation
- D. To reduce skin secretion

25. All of the following are the functions of skin, EXCEPT:

- A. Excretion
- B. Protection
- C. Sensation
- D. Storage

26. Which among the following body parts of the newborn gets accumulated with dirt easily?

- A. Hair
- B. Hands
- C. Legs
- D. Skin creases

27. Which among the following statements is True about diaper care?

- A. A cloth diaper can be used for 8 hours.
- B. Use of any soap to perineal area can be used.
- C. Use of petroleum jelly reduces rashes.
- D. Use of powder on the perineum after diaper care is safe.

28. How should the water temperature be assessed for cleaning the perineum of a newborn? A. Back of the palm
B. Elbow
C. Index fingers D.
Little finger
29. Which of the following changes can be identified by the mother in the newborn during diaper care? A. Body Color
B. Body Temperature C.
Urine Color
D. All of the above
30. Which of the following materials is used to clean the umbilical cord in a newborn?
A. Oil
B. Powder
C. soap
D. Warm water
31. Identify the proper direction of cleaning newborn eyes.
- A. Down to up B. Inner to outer C. Outer to inner D. Up to down
32. Mrs. S is having a female baby who is 3 days old. Which direction of wiping should be used by her to clean the anal region of the baby after defecation?
A. Back to front
B. Front to back
C. Thighs first,
D. Any direction

Scoring

Each right answer is scored one.

0-10 score: inadequate knowledge

11-21 score: moderately adequate knowledge

22-32 score: adequate knowledge

Tool 3: Observation checklist on Newborn care

Instruction: The investigator will observe the procedure on thermoregulation, breastfeeding, and personal hygiene performed by mothers on newborns, and Places a tick in the yes or no column by observing the presence or absence of the step.

Birth weight :

Gender:

Sl. No	Steps	Yes	No
Thermoregulation (Wrapping)	1. Warms the hands		
	2. Places the cloth on a firm surface		
	3. Folds one corner of the cloth		
	4. Positions the newborn such that the newborn's head is on the folded corner.		
	5. Wraps the head and then wraps the cloth over one side of the newborn's chest.		
	6. Repeats for the other side.		
	7. Secures the feet by tucking the lower corner over them		
Breastfeeding (position)	Position the newborn for feeding.		
	1. Sits straight and uses a pillow to support her back.		
	2. Cleans the breast cloth soaked in warm water.		
	3. Uses a pillow under the newborn		
	4. Rest the newborn's head on her elbow joint and the newborn's body on her forearm		
	5. The newborn's chest should touch the mother's chest.		
	1. Position to hold breast: 'C' position: Grasp		
	Latch		
	1. Sits straight and uses a pillow to support her back.		
	2. Uses a pillow under the newborn		
	3. The newborn's chest is facing the mother's chest		
	4. Inserts breast inside newborn's mouth when the mouth is wide open		
	5. Makes sure that most of the black part of the breast is inside the newborn's mouth.		
	6. Places her little finger inside the newborn's mouth after feeding the newborn, so that it can prevent pulling of the nipple		
	Position the newborn for burping		
1. Places the newborn on the shoulder			
2. Rubs or taps the newborn's back from down to the top			
Personal hygiene			
-Diaper care	1. Takes a square cloth		
	2. One corner of the square cloth should faces mother.		
	3. Folds the left corner approximately to the center, then the right corner folds to the center.		
	4. Folds the upper triangular corner over the previous folds.		
	5. Folds bottom corner, fold it front again.		
	6. Places the newborn on the cloth diaper prepared.		
	7. Folds the bottom corner of the newborn and wraps the side corners around the waist. Secures it.		

Total Score: 28

Scoring and Interpretation

Each correct step gets one score.